

A Study to Assess the Knowledge of Mothers with School Age Children Regarding Child Abuse and Its Prevention in Bhucho Mandi, Bathinda (Punjab)

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ABSTRACT

Child is a human between the stage of birth and puberty the legal definition of child generally refers to a minor, otherwise known as a person younger than the age of majority. Abuse most commonly refers to the use or treatment of something or someone that is harmful or the lack of proper care of these. A non-experimental descriptive study was conducted to assess the knowledge of mothers with school age children regarding child abuse and its prevention in Bhucho Mandi, Bathinda. The study was conducted on 60 mothers with children in the age group of 6-12 years. Knowledge of mothers was assessed with the help of structured questionnaire. Convenient non-probability sampling technique was used in this study. The study revealed that out of 60, the level of knowledge of mothers 22(36.7%) were having inadequate knowledge, 23(38.3%) were having moderate knowledge, 15(25%) were having adequate knowledge. Among socio-demographic variables, educational status of mother and occupational status came out to be significantly associated with level of knowledge.

Keywords: Knowledge, Mothers.

BACKGROUND

Child abuse means any act or failure to act on the part of a parent or caretaker which results in death, serious physical or emotional harm, sexual abuse or exploitation or an act or failure to act which presents risk of serious harm.

Child abuse includes physical violence (75%), sexual molestations (20%), mental and emotional (5%) maltreatment with negligence, deprivation and lack of opportunity. The children are abused at home, school, day care centers and working places by the caretakers and other adults.

Not all children exposed to similar experiences are affected in the same way. For some children and young people, the effects of child abuse and neglect may be chronic and debilitating; others may experience less adverse outcomes. Risk factors that may contribute to abuse and neglect includes socio-economic disadvantage, social isolation, large families, living in dangerous neighbourhoods, a caregiver with depression or alcohol or drug dependence and whether the child has a disability.

Preventing child abuse requires a multi-sectoral approach. Ways to help prevent Child Abuse includes:

- Be a nurturing parent.
- Help a friend, neighbour or relative.
- Help yourself.
- Get involved: Ask your community leaders, clergy, library and schools to develop services to meet the needs of healthy children and families.
- If your baby cries, don't shake your baby.
- Help to develop parenting resources at your local library.
- Promote programs in school: Teaching children, parents and teachers prevention strategies can help to keep children safe.

-Monitor your child's television, video and internet viewing / usage.

-Volunteer at a local child abuse prevention program.

-Report suspected abuse or neglect.

Problem statement

A study to assess the knowledge of mothers with school age children regarding child abuse and its prevention in Bhucho Mandi, Bathinda.

Purpose

Through this research researcher wanted to assess the knowledge of mothers regarding child abuse and its prevention.

Objectives

- To assess the knowledge of mothers with school aged children regarding child abuse and its prevention.
- To find out the association between the knowledge of mothers with school-aged children regarding child abuse and its prevention with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Assumptions

- School age children may be in more risk of child abuse.
- Mothers may have some knowledge regarding child abuse and its prevention.

Review of Literature

- Literature related to knowledge of mothers on child abuse.
- Literature related to prevention on child abuse.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Approach: Quantitative research approach was adopted.

Research Design: Descriptive non-experimental research design was adopted. Variables under study

Dependent Variable: Knowledge of mother.

Demographic Variables: Age, Gender, Religion, Area of Residence, Educational status of mother, Marital status, Occupational status of mother, Monthly Family Income.

Research Setting: Study was conducted in Bhucho Mandi, Bathinda.

Target Population: The target population of the study were 60 mothers with children of 6-12 years of age taken from Bhucho Mandi, Bathinda

Sample Size

The sample for present study was 60 mothers of school aged children in the age group of 6-12 years of age.

Sampling Technique

The sample was selected by convenient non-probability sampling technique.

Sampling Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- Mothers with children in the age group 6-12 years.
- Mothers who will participate in this study.
- Mothers who knows Punjabi.

Exclusion Criteria

- Mothers who are not willing to participate in research study.

Selection and Development of the Tool

To accomplish the objectives of the study, the research tool was constructed in following two sections:

Section A: Socio-demographic variables

Section B: Structured Knowledge questionnaire

Section A: Demographic variables:

This section consist of 8 items for obtaining personal information about children i.e. Age, Gender, Religion, Area of Residence, Educational status of Mother, Marital status, Occupational status of mother, Monthly Family Income.

Section B: Structured Knowledge questionnaire:

In this study, structured knowledge questionnaire consists of 20 items related to child abuse and its prevention. A score value of one (1) was allotted to each correct response and zero (0) for every incorrect response. Total score of structured questionnaire was 20. An answer key was also prepared.

CRITERION MEASURE

- 14-20 Inadequate
- 7-14..... Moderately adequate
- 0-7..... Inadequate

Content validity of the Tool

Content validity of the socio-demographic variables was determined by expert’s opinion. The socio- demographic variables and knowledge questionnaire was given to the Medical and Nursing experts in the field of Maternal and Child Health and language experts in English and Punjabi (participant information sheet, consent form and socio-demographic variables). As per the guidance and suggestions from the experts, the suggested amendments were made in the tool.

Reliability of Tool

Reliability of tool was estimated by test-retest reliability method. The reliability came out be 0.7. Thus, the tool was reliable.

Pilot study

Pilot study was conducted on 6 mothers selected as per the sampling criteria.

Ethical Considerations

Participants were informed about the study and verbal consent was given to each participant and the study was conducted after obtaining approval from Principal, College of Nursing, Adesh University Bathinda.

Description about Intervention

The study participants were the mothers who had children of age group, i.e. 6-12 years of age. The tool as described earlier was structured knowledge questionnaire.

Plan of Analysis

Data analysis was done as per the objectives of the study. The data was analyzed by using SPSS version 20, by descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage and inferential statistics such as Chi-square was used to find out association between variables. Data has been represented in the form of tables.

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage distribution of socio-demographic variables N=60

S. NO.	VARIABLES	f	%
1.	Age (in Years)		
	21-34	33	55
	31-40	27	45
2.	Religion		
	Sikh	49	81.7
	Hindu	11	18.3
3.	Educational status of mothers		
	No Formal Education	9	15
	10th	32	53.3
	12th	12	20
	Graduate and Postgraduate	7	11.7
4.	Marital Status		
	Married	54	90
	Widow	6	10
5.	Occupational status		
	Govt.Employee	7	11.7
	Private Employee	18	30
	Labourer	11	18.3
	Housewife	24	40
6.	Monthly Family Income (in Rs)		
	≤5000	6	10
	5001-10,000	28	46.6
	10,001-20,000	16	26.7
	≥20,001	10	16.7

Section-II

Objective I- To assess the knowledge of mothers with school-aged children regarding child abuse and its prevention.

Table-II

Level of Knowledge	f	%
Inadequate	22	36.7
Moderately adequate	23	38.3
Adequate	15	25

Table II revealed that majority of 23 (38.3%) mothers were having moderately adequate knowledge, 22(36.7%) mothers were having Inadequate and 15(25%) were having adequate knowledge.

Objective II- To find out the association between the knowledge of mothers regarding child abuse and its prevention

with their selected socio-demographic variables.

It was evident from the table that chi square value computed for demographic variables. Educational status of mothers and

Occupational status showed statistically significant associated with the level of knowledge regarding child abuse and its prevention.

Table 3: Association of socio-demographic variables

N-60	I.K	M.A	A.K			
				χ^2	df	p-value
Age (in Years)						
21-34	148	12	7	1.158	2	0.560
31-40		11	8	(NS)		
Religion						
Sikh	19	17	13	1.498	2	0.473
Hindu	3	6	2	(NS)		
Educational status of mothers						
No Formal Education	8	1	0	17.053		0.009
10th	9	16	7	(S)	6	
12th	4	4	4			
Graduate and Postgraduate	1	2	4			
Marital Status						
Married	19	23	12	4.545	2	0.103
Widow	3	0	3	(NS)		
Occupational status						
Govt. Employee	1	0	6			
Private Employee	6	6	6	19.806	6	0.003
Labourer	5	5	1	(S)		
Housewife	10	12	2			
Monthly Family Income (in Rs)						
≤5000	5	1	0		6	0.017
5001-10,000	12	12	4	15.385		
10,001-20,000	5	5	6	(NS)		
≥20,001	0	5	5			

DISCUSSION

1. The first objective is to assess the knowledge of mothers with school aged children regarding child abuse and its prevention.

The study revealed that majority of 23 (38.3%) mothers were having moderately adequate knowledge, 22(36.7%) mothers were having inadequate and 15(25%) were having adequate knowledge.

The findings were similar to the study (Thangavelu SN) conducted a study to assess the level of knowledge regarding child abuse among mothers. The data was collected from revealed that 17 mothers (85%) were having moderately adequate knowledge, 3 mothers (15%) were having inadequate knowledge and 0% were having adequate knowledge.

The similar study conducted by (Brar MK) on assessment of knowledge regarding prevention of child abuse among mothers of fewer than five children. Findings reported that majority of 50 (50%) mothers of under five children had average knowledge

regarding prevention of child abuse and minimum 12 (12%) had good knowledge regarding prevention of child abuse.

2. The second objective is to find out the association between the knowledge of mothers regarding child abuse and its prevention with their selected socio-demographic variables.

The study revealed that educational status of mothers and occupational status showed significantly associated. The similar study conducted by (Mekala.P, Jeyalakshmi.S, Barathidasan.R) on assessment of knowledge on child abuse among mothers of adolescent girls. The results revealed that there was highly significant association with selected demographic variables such as educational status and occupational status

IMPLICATIONS Nursing Education

1. Nursing education need to be strengthened to enable nursing students to know about current knowledge on child abuse and its prevention.

2. Nursing curriculum should provide clinical experience on conduction to provide education regarding prevention of child abuse in various settings eg. Community, wards and OPD etc.

Nursing Research

1. The findings of the study serve as a basis for the nursing professionals and the students to conduct further studies in different aspects of prevention of child abuse.

Recommendations: Based on the results of the study, following recommendation are made:

- Further researches can be conducted.
- The study can be replicated on a large sample to validate and generalize its findings.
- A multi centre study could be done.
- A true experimental (RCT) study could be done.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the findings of the study, it was concluded that majority of the subject had moderately adequate knowledge regarding child abuse and its prevention.

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